

Analysis of Promotion, Tuition Fees and Service Quality toward Customer Satisfaction and its Implications on the Repurchase Intention (Case Study of Amaniyah Tutoring Institute)

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Abstract:- This study evaluates and analyzes promotion, price, and service quality towards customer satisfaction and the implication of the repurchase intention. By census, 168 questionnaires were filled by the parents of Amaniyah Tutoring Institute. The research approach is implemented quantitatively, with correlational design. The analysis technique used in this study is the Structural Equation Model (SEM) by the help of the Smart-PLS 3.0 program.

Result reveals that promotion, tuition fees, and service quality has positive and significant toward customer satisfaction. Promotion and tuition fees have positive and significant effect toward customer satisfaction, while service quality does not. Promotion and service quality have positive and significant effect toward repurchase intention, while tuition fees do not. Customer satisfaction is also not able to mediate promotion, tuition fees and service quality toward repurchase intention.

Keywords:- Promotion, Tuition Fees, Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, Repurchase Intention, Non-Formal Education.

I. INTRODUCTION

The quality of Indonesian education experienced a significant decline when Distance Learning was implemented by the government since the beginning of the Corona *Virus Disease* 2019 (Covid-19) pandemic (Larasati, 2021) This condition encourages parents to provide additional lessons outside of school. Amaniyah Tutoring Institute is one of the solutions to improve students' learning achievement.

In 2022, Amaniyah Tutoring Institute experienced a growth of 101 new students but 40 students withdrew. The decline in the number of students resulted in various problems that had to be faced by the management of Amaniyah Tutoring Institute. The decline in profits force management to eliminate four tutors. Therefore, the right effort and service marketing strategy are needed so that parents decide to do repurchase intention on Amaniyah Tutoring Institute.

Based on previous research, there are several variables that support repurchase intention; discounts (Qibtiyah et al., 2021), service quality (Aris, 2020), brand awareness (Ilyas et al., 2020), service marketing mix which includes *products, prices, promotions*, and places, people, physical facilities, and

processes (Lahtinen et al., 2020) Based on preliminary surveys, promotions, prices and service quality are variables that have the highest scores. Then the variable will be examined into an independent variable. Customer satisfaction shows a significant effect on interest in repurchase intentions (Choi et al., 2019; Phuong & Trang, 2018). Service quality affects customer satisfaction. Consumer satisfaction effects the decision to re-choose. Then consumer satisfaction will be examined into mediation variable.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Promotions

Promotion is a strong variable of the marketing mix. Promotion acts as the core of the marketing mix strategy. Educational institutions use promotions to transmit information about academic activities. Promotion acts as a strategy that helps publicize the institution to attract parents and/or students.

Promotion in this study is a marketing activity to inform, effects/persuade, and remind parents directly or indirectly about various learning programs in Amaniyah Tutoring Institute.

The promotion mix has eight elements: advertising, paid forms of non-personal presentation and promotion of ideas, goods or services by clear sponsorship through the media; sales promotion, various short-term incentives to encourage trial or purchase of products or services including consumer promotions (such as samples, coupons, and premiums); company-sponsored events and experiences, activities and programs designed to create interaction with consumers; public relations and publicity, various programs geared towards image building; personal sales, face-to-face interactions conducted by the company's salespeople to prospective buyers; direct marketing, direct relationships with individual consumers to elicit immediate responses and achieve lasting consumer relationships; interactive marketing, online activities and programs that engage consumers to raise awareness, improve image, or create sales of products and services; marketing and word of mouth, oral, written, and electronic communication between communities related to excellence or experience of buying or using service products (Kotler & Armstrong, 2016).

B. Tuition Fees

Tuition fees are an amount of money paid by a student's parents and/or guardians to consume a proportion of the value of educational services. Tuition fees are effected by payment flexibility, related to the ability of learning institutions to provide methods and mediums of payment of tuition fees (Ratiu & Avram, 2013); affordability of education costs; and the appropriateness of education costs and the quality of education (Kotler & Amstrong, 2016).

C. Service Quality

Service quality is a form of assessment of parents of students on the suitability of the level of service of perceived design quality (perceived services) with the level of expected service (expected service).

Consumer perception of service quality can be measured through the SERVQUAL concept which includes direct evidence, related to aspects that can be felt directly using the five human senses; reliability, relating to the company's ability to deliver services based on what is promised; responsiveness, emphasizing speed and accuracy of service; assurance, emphasizing the safety and security of the service experience; empathy, relating to understanding, personal attention given by service providers to consumers (Zeithaml et al. 2018).

D. Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is the level of feeling as a result of comparing the quality of service experienced with the expectations of parents. If the quality of service is in line with expectations, then parents will feel satisfied. If the quality of service is not up to expectations, parents will feel disappointed.

Hawkins and Lonney classify indicators of consumer satisfaction formation consisting of conformity of expectations, related to the performance of services expected by a customer with that perceived by consumers; interest in revisiting or willingness to reuse; willingness to recommend; have the desire not to move to another product/service; satisfied with the final product / service received / purchased (Tjiptono, 2015).

E. Repurchase Intention

Repurchase intention in this study is the interest and/or action of the parents to re-select the Amaniyah Tutoring Institute learning program, because the parents are satisfied with the s appropriateness of expectations and the performance of the chosen learning program. Schiffman & Kanuk (2013) differentiated indicators of repurchase intention: attraction, concentration and feelings of pleasure; desire, the presence of an urge to want to have; confidence, the individual's feeling of confidence in the quality, usability and profitability of the product to be purchased.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Based on the literature review, the framework in this study is as follows:

Picture 1: Conceptual Framework

Based on the framework, the research hypothesis is formulated as follows:

- H1: Promotion has a positive and significant effects toward customer satisfaction.
- H2: Tuition fees have a positive and significant effects toward consumer satisfaction.
- H3: The service quality has a positive and significant effects toward customer satisfaction.
- H4: The promotion has a positive and significant effects toward repurchase intention.
- H5: Tuition fees have a positive and significant effects toward repurchase intention.
- H6: The service quality has a positive and significant effects toward repurchase intention.
- H7: Customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effects towards repurchase intention.

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Research Desain

This study adopted a quantitative approach. The research design used was correlational, with the aim of testing hypotheses about the effect of promotion, tuition fees, and service quality on parental satisfaction variables and their implications towards repurchase intention. The data collection method used is *surveys*.

The instrument data collected in the form of literature studies. The questionnaires are distributed offline and online. The analysis technique used in this study is the Structural Equation Model (SEM) with the help of the Smart-PLS 3.0 application.

B. Population and Sample

The population in this study was parents of students who had enrolled their children at Amaniyah Tutoring Institute, and continued to study for more than three months. The parents of students in Amaniyah Tutoring Institute are 168 (one hundred and sixty-eight) people.

Given that the population size is relatively small due to the criteria applied, the entire population will be used as a research sample. The sampling technique used is saturated sampling, commonly known as census. A total of 168 respondents will be examined.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. SEM Analysis by SmartPLS

➤ **Outer Model Evaluation**

Researchers tested the measuring instrument used for this study; questionnaires, to determine the validity and reliability of linking indicators with latent variables. To test validity, convergent validity and discriminant validity tests are required. As for testing reliability, composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha measurements are needed.

➤ **Convergent Validity Cross Loading**

The first stage of this evaluation assesses the criteria of convergent validity. An indicator is declared to have good validity if it has a loading factor value greater than 0.70 (Hair, et al., 2021). The loading factors of each construct are presented in the following table.

Table 1: Convergent Validity Cross Loading

Construct	Promotion	Tuition Fees	Service Quality	Customer Satisfaction	Repurchase Intention
P2	0,916	0,794	0,756	0,882	0,731
P3	0,846	0,700	0,726	0,783	0,772
P5	0,844	0,639	0,627	0,750	0,761
P6	0,777	0,635	0,729	0,707	0,697
P7	0,890	0,825	0,711	0,842	0,665
P8	0,875	0,748	0,648	0,791	0,639
P9	0,902	0,742	0,828	0,875	0,783
TF11	0,810	0,909	0,761	0,845	0,640
TF12	0,728	0,877	0,818	0,788	0,606
TF2	0,816	0,964	0,857	0,876	0,689
TF3	0,689	0,838	0,705	0,743	0,589
TF4	0,658	0,791	0,641	0,713	0,530
TF5	0,700	0,852	0,721	0,737	0,557
TF7	0,757	0,915	0,775	0,798	0,653
SQ10	0,781	0,816	0,920	0,827	0,728
SQ4	0,770	0,828	0,915	0,851	0,721
SQ5	0,648	0,650	0,851	0,706	0,635
SQ6	0,731	0,769	0,870	0,800	0,654
SQ7	0,749	0,817	0,897	0,827	0,690
SQ8	0,805	0,789	0,937	0,829	0,794
SQ9	0,750	0,744	0,917	0,803	0,754
CS1	0,842	0,846	0,856	0,943	0,705
CS10	0,888	0,882	0,892	0,969	0,753
CS5	0,870	0,886	0,888	0,954	0,717
CS6	0,815	0,787	0,673	0,834	0,597
CS7	0,727	0,606	0,589	0,751	0,558
CS9	0,900	0,821	0,906	0,949	0,786
RI3	0,773	0,692	0,768	0,753	0,844
RI4	0,748	0,599	0,696	0,666	0,939
RI5	0,749	0,644	0,723	0,699	0,927
RI6	0,682	0,500	0,558	0,576	0,858
RI7	0,805	0,685	0,799	0,741	0,942

Source: Output Program SmartPLS 3.0.

All indicators get the highest value in each intended construct. Thus, each construct in this study is valid. The next

step is to examine the *Fornell-Larcker Criterion*, presented in the following table.

➤ *Discriminant Validity Fornell-Larcker*

Table 2: *Discriminant Validity Fornell-Larcker*

Construct	Tuition Fees	Customer Satisfaction	Repurchase Intention	Service Quality	Promotion
Tuition Fees	0,866				
Customer Satisfaction	0,777	0,900			
Repurchase Intention	0,677	0,641	0,898		
Service Quality	0,852	0,704	0,769	0,901	
Promotion	0,837	0,861	0,824	0,829	0,866

Source: *Output Program SmartPLS 3.0.*

The root square of each AVE construct must be greater than the highest correlation with other constructs. So the results of this calculation already fulfilled the *Fornell-Larcker Criterion*.

➤ *Composite Reability and Cronbach Alpha*

In SmartPLS, reliability are tested by composite reliability and reinforced with Cronbach Alpha. Determination of composite reliability based on the value of composite reliability; $\rho_c > 0,7$ means that the construct has high

reliability or reliable and $\rho_c > 0.6$ means quite reliable. The alpha coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha) is calculated in terms of the average of the intercorrelations between items that measure the concept. The closer the alpha coefficient is to the value of 1, the higher the reliability of internal consistency. In general, a reliability of $> 0,60$ is poor, a reliability of $0,70$ is acceptable, and $> 0,80$ considered as good.

The following is the reliability calculation of each variable.

Table 3: *Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability, Average Variance Extracted (AVE)*

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Information
Promotion	0,944	0,954	0,749	Reliabel
Tuition Fees	0,933	0,947	0,750	Reliabel
Service Quality	0,961	0,968	0,812	Reliabel
Customer Satisfaction	0,767	0,895	0,810	Reliabel
Repurchase Intention	0,919	0,943	0,807	Reliabel

Source: *Output Program SmartPLS 3.0.*

B. *Evaluasi Inner Model*

Structural model evaluation is performed using R-square (R^2) for dependent constructs, Stone-Geisser Q-square test for *predictive relevance*, and t-test and significance of structural

path parameter coefficients. By using the help of the SmartPLS 3.0 program application, booth strapping results as follows.

Table 4: *Path Coefficients and R Square*

Parameter	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics	P Values	Decision
Promotion -> Customer Satisfaction	0,772	0,778	0,087	8,838	0,000	Accepted
Tuition Fees-> Customer Satisfaction	0,282	0,283	0,084	3,358	0,000	Accepted
Service Quality-> Customer Satisfaction	-0,177	-0,183	0,061	2,913	0,002	Rejected
Promotion -> Repurchase Intention	0,862	0,874	0,113	7,605	0,000	Accepted
Tuition Fees-> Repurchase Intention	-0,199	-0,199	0,060	3,302	0,001	Rejected
Service Quality-> Repurchase Intention	0,370	0,365	0,072	5,104	0,000	Accepted
Customer Satisfaction -> Repurchase Intention	-0,207	-0,214	0,076	2,723	0,003	Rejected

Source: *Output Program SmartPLS 3.0.*

Inner model evaluation is a relationships analysis between constructs. This evaluation determines the acceptance and rejection of the hypothesis. The relationship between constructs is acceptable if T-Statistics value is greater than 1.96 with a significance value of 0.05 (one

tailed). The results of estimated relationship between constructs as follows:

- Hypothesis 1 – Promotion has a positive and significant effects toward consumer satisfaction. The coefficient parameter for the promotion variable to consumer

satisfaction of 0.772 is close to one, which means there is a positive effect. The results of the promotion estimation coefficient test on consumer satisfaction are 0.778 with a T-Statistic value of 8.838 > 1.96 and a standard deviation of 0.087. Then the P-Value value is 0.000 < 0.05, so promotion has a statistically significant effect. Thus, promotion (X1) has a positive and significant effects toward consumer satisfaction (Z). H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted.

- Hypothesis 2 – The tuition fees have a positive and significant effects toward consumer satisfaction. The path efficiency value for the variable cost of education to consumer satisfaction is 0.282, close to one then there is a positive effect. Based on booth strapping, the estimated results of tuition fees toward consumer satisfaction gave a value of 0.283 with a T-Statistic value of 3.358 > 1.96, with a standard deviation of 0.084. Then the P-Value value is 0.000 < 0.05, so the tuition fees have statistically significant effects. Thus, the tuition fees (X2) have a positive and significant effects toward consumer satisfaction (Z). H0 is rejected and H2 is accepted.
- Hypothesis 3 – Service quality has a negative and significant effect on customer satisfaction. The parameter for the variable of service quality to customer satisfaction is -0.177, the coefficient value has negative connotations. Indicates that the quality of service does not have a good effect on customer satisfaction. Based on the bootstrap test, the results of the coefficient test of service quality toward customer satisfaction are -0.183 with a T-Statistic value of 2.913 > 1.96 and a standard deviation of 0.061. So, the P-Value value is 0.002 < 0.05, so that the direct effect of service quality on customer satisfaction is meaningful or statistically significant. Thus, service quality (X3) has a negative and significant effects toward customer satisfaction (Z). H0 is accepted and H3 is rejected.
- Hypothesis 4 – Promotion has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention. The parameter for the promotion variable to the repurchase intention is 0.862, the coefficient value of this path has a positive connotation close to one. Based on the bootstrap test, the results of the promotion estimation coefficient test on the repurchase intention are 0.874 with a T-Statistic value of 7.605 > 1.96 and a standard deviation of 0.113. Thus the P value is 0.000 < 0.05, so the direct effects of promotion toward repurchase

intention is meaningful or statistically significant. Thus, promotion (X1) has a positive and significant effects toward repurchase intention (Y). H0 is rejected and H4 is accepted.

- Hypothesis 5 – The tuition fees have negative and significant effects toward repurchase intention. The parameter for the promotion toward repurchases intention is -0.199, the coefficient value of this path has a negative connotation close to minus one, then the cost of education has no effects toward repurchase intention. Based on the bootstrap test, the coefficient test results of estimating the tuition fees toward repurchase intention are -0.199 with a T-Statistic value of 3.302 > 1.96 and a standard deviation of 0.060. The P value is 0.001 < 0.05, so the direct effects of tuition fees toward repurchase intention is meaningful or statistically significant. Thus, the tuition fees (X2) have a negative and significant effects on repurchase intention (Y). H0 is accepted and H5 is rejected.
- Hypothesis 6 – Service quality has a positive and significant effects toward the repurchase intention. The parameter for the service quality variable against repurchase intention is 0.370, the coefficient value of this path has a positive connotation close to one. Based on the bootstrap test conducted, the results of the coefficient test of service quality estimation of repurchase intention are 0.365 with a T-Statistic value of 5.104 > 1.96 and a standard deviation of 0.072. Then the P value is 0.000 < 0.05, so the direct effects of promotion on repurchase intention is meaningful or statistically significant. Thus, the service quality (X3) has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention (Y). H0 is rejected and H6 is accepted.

Furthermore, there is a mediation test that evaluates the effect of mediation variable. There is variable that effects and contained between two constructs. This relates to the effects produced by exogenous variables that also change mediator variables that produce changes in relationships with endogenous variables in a model (Hair et al., 2017). The evaluation of mediation is calculated with a significance of 0.05 (two tailed).

The results of the significance test of indirect effects on this study are presented in the following table.

Table 5: Output Specific Indirect Effects

Parameter	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Promotion -> Customer Satisfaction -> Repurchase Intention	-0,160	-0,167	0,066	2,419	0,016
Tuition Fees -> Customer Satisfaction -> Repurchase Intention	-0,058	-0,059	0,026	2,203	0,028
Service Quality -> Customer Satisfaction -> Repurchase Intention	0,037	0,038	0,018	2,078	0,038

Source: Output Program SmartPLS 3.0

Based on the results of statistical calculations, concluded that:

- Hypothesis 7 – Consumer satisfaction (Z) has no role in mediating the relationship between promotion (X1), tuition

fees (X2), and quality of service (X3) toward repurchase intention (Y).

The parameter for promotion toward repurchases intention through consumer satisfaction was -0.160, the parameter tuition fees toward repurchase intention through consumer satisfaction was -0.058, while the parameter service quality toward repurchase intention through consumer satisfaction was 0.037. The efficient value of pathways for promotion and tuition fees has negative connotations. This indicates that consumer satisfaction cannot mediate both promotion and tuition fees over the repurchase intention.

The promotion variable to the decision to repurchase intention mediated by consumer satisfaction has a T-Statistic value of 2.419 > 1.96 and a standard deviation of 0.066, then the P-Value is 0.016 < 0.05. Then the indirect effects of promotion on repurchase intention through the mediation of consumer satisfaction is meaningful or statistically significant. The variable tuition fees toward repurchase

intention mediated by consumer satisfaction has a T-Statistic value of 2.203 > 1.96 and a standard deviation of 0.026 < 0.05 then the P-Value is 0.028 < 0.05. So the indirect effect of education costs on repurchase intention through the mediation of consumer satisfaction is meaningful or statistically significant. The variable of service quality on the decision to repurchase intention mediated with customer satisfaction has a T-Statistic value of 2.078 > 1.96 and a standard deviation of 0.018 < 0.05 then the P-Value is 0.038 < 0.05. So the indirect effects of service quality on repurchase intention through mediation of customer satisfaction is meaningful or statistically significant.

Consumer Satisfaction (Z) does not mediate the relationship among Promotion (X1), Tuition Fee (X2), and Quality of Service (X3) to the Re-Election Decision (Y). H0 is accepted and H7 is rejected.

In this study, the condition of *no mediation effects* occurred. There is only direct effects.

C. Discussion

➤ Characteristics of respondents

Table 6: Respondents Identity

Respondent Identity	Number of Respondent	Percentage
Age		
26 – 30 years old	30	17,9%
31 – 35 years old	41	24,4%
36 – 40 years old	64	38%
> 41 years old	33	19,6%
Total	168	100%
Chosen Program		
Pra Calis (Pre reading and writing)	3	1,8%
Ahe (Anak Hebat / reading)	83	49,4%
Mapel (Les Mata Pelajaran/ all subjects)	51	30,4%
BEC (Brilliant English Course)	11	6,5%
QMF (Quantum Math Fun)	18	10,7%
Science (Biology, Physics, Chemical)	2	1,2%
Total	168	100,0%

Source: Questioner

Most respondents (38%) were aged 36 – 40 years old. This age range is included of millennial generation, born in 1981 – 1996. The millennial generation lives in changing from conventional to modern. One of the characteristics of this generation is high digital intelligence and love to collaborate through social media.

Meanwhile, the most popular learning program is Ahe (Anak hebat/ reading program), as much as 49.4%. This program is devoted to learning to read and write with a minimum age of 4 years old. One of the reasons many parents register their children to learn to read and write is the Circular Letter of the Directorate General of Primary and Secondary

Education Management no. 1839/C.C2/TU/2009, which does not allow literacy and numeracy to be the main curriculum of Early Childhood Education and Kindergarten. Then Ahe should be of main concern to management.

➤ The Influence of Promotion toward Customer Satisfaction

Parameter estimation and hypothesis testing previously showed that the promotion carried out by Amaniyah Tutoring Institute has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction. The results of the study are in accordance with previous research conducted (Verma & Sing, 2017; Khatab et al., 2019).

The results showed that the promotion applied by Amaniyah Tutoring Institute to parents of students had given maximum results. The dimension that provides the greatest satisfaction is the existence of scholarship vouchers, and free registration, as well as discount coupons for competition prizes. This indicator, which is a dimension of sales promotion, contributes greatly to the satisfaction of parents of students. Implicitly, Amaniyah Tutoring Institute consumers still like vouchers and discounts. So, Amaniyah Tutoring Institute should do promotions using vouchers and discount coupons continuously to increase consumer satisfaction. The better the promotion, the higher level of consumer satisfaction.

Another promotional aspect that determines consumer satisfaction is the presence of good reviews to family / relatives / peers about the quality of Bimbel Amaniyah Jakarta. The power of *word of mouth* is the key to variable promotion. Another indicator that shapes the satisfaction of parents of students is. Interactive marketing with social media content indicators. Parents are interested to follow, change and/or add learning programs after seeing content on Instagram, Facebook and YouTube accounts, thus causing satisfaction in parents. In this context, developing promotions through online-based interactive marketing should be considered to increase consumer satisfaction.

➤ *The Influence of Tuition Fees toward Customer Satisfaction*

Previous hypothesis testing shows that the cost of education has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction. The results of this study are in accordance with Leonnard's (2018) research that the perceived value of money has a positive effect on student satisfaction in the field of educational services. The findings are also consistent with previous research conducted by Verma & Sing (2017), and Choi et al., (2019). These positive effects shows that the more competitive the cost of education, the more satisfied consumers will be. The indicators that have the greatest effects are the affordability of education costs, especially in learning modules and the suitability of education costs with benefits in registration fees. The price of learning modules offered by Amaniyah Tutoring Institute meets the standards of student parent satisfaction. Given that students must purchase a new module when they pass a certain level, the length of time it takes to graduate from that level should also be considered. Another implication of the results of this study is that the sooner students graduate and enter higher levels, the sooner parents should buy new modules. So far, the appropriateness of the time required by parents to purchase learning modules also has provided satisfaction (Rațiu & Avram, 2013).

Another indicator that supports the satisfaction of parent is the amount of tuition fees that match the benefits they feel. The amount of tuition is not considered too expensive so that it can still be reached by parents, and it is not too cheap so that it reduces the *prestige* of Bimbel Amaniyah.

➤ *The Influence of Service Quality toward Customer Satisfaction*

The results of parameter estimation and hypothesis testing previously showed that service quality negatively affects customer satisfaction. Similar research has been conducted by Maimunah (2019). Service quality does not affect customer satisfaction. In the field of educational services, this may happen.

Based on the results of the study, the strongest factor that indicates this is that the *call center* is considered not responsive to reply to messages sent by parents. Practice in the field, the *call center* is managed by all tutors with one tutor in charge. Tutors are required to be observant in dividing time well to answer messages sent by parents, even though they are teaching.

Another factor of service quality that affects parental satisfaction is, not all tutors can answer questions about all learning programs offered by Amaniyah Tutoring Institute. The fact in the field, not all tutors can teach all learning programs, so their knowledge of learning programs still has to be improved.

Another factor, the performance and quality of tutoring is measured by the good achievement of student learning outcomes taught. The main problem is that the quality and achievement of student learning outcomes cannot be equalized. In fact, every child is born unique and sometimes special. Based on the theory by Gardner, there are nine types of human intelligence (Barokah, 2020). Every human being can have multiple intelligences, but cannot master all nine types of intelligence. The tutor cannot force the achievement of the Quantum Math Fun (Numeric Intelligence) learning program as well as the student masters the Brilliant English Course (Linguistic Intelligence) learning program. Thus, the measurement of the level of parental satisfaction will be bias if it is based on the learning achievement of each student.

➤ *The Influence of Promotion toward Repurchase Intention*

The results of parameter estimation and hypothesis testing that have been carried out show that promotion has a positive and significant effect on the repurchase intention. This is in accordance with research conducted by Mahmoud (2018), which shows that green promotion in students has a positive and significant effect on the repurchase intention.

Based on the test results, the promotion carried out by the management of Amaniyah Tutoring Institute has run very well and on target, thus having a significant positive effect. One indicator that exerts effects in the repurchase intention parents is events and experiences. The existence of joint activities involving prospective parents and prospective students will provide awareness and experience marketing. Experience marketing will ultimately shape engagement with Bimbel Amaniyah, so it becomes one of the factors that effects their decision to join Amaniyah Tutoring Institute (Amoako et al., 2021).

When held activity involving Amaniyah Tutoring Institute management and parents as consumers, the management often provides door prizes and winning prizes in the form of scholarship vouchers (discounts). Parents can use this scholarship voucher. In the end, parents of students are interested in continuing the study program they are pursuing because of this scholarship voucher. The same findings are found in the research of Qibtiyah et al. (2021), which shows that discounts have a positive and significant effects on repurchase interest. So, providing sales promotions like this is effective to continue.

In addition, parents are interested in continuing to follow, change and/or add learning programs after viewing content on Amaniyah's Instagram, Facebook and YouTube accounts. In accordance with the findings of Rațiu & Avram, n.d., (2013), that media can be used as publicity suggestions for various promotions. So interactive marketing through social media must still be done carefully to maintain these significant effects.

➤ *The Influence of Tuition Fees toward Repurchase Intention*

The results of parameter estimation and hypothesis testing previously showed that the tuition fees negatively affect the repurchase intention. The results of this test are not in accordance with previous research conducted by Mahmoud (2017) which proves that green prices in students have a positive and significant effect.

This interprets that the amount of education fees has no effects at all on parents repurchase intention. The theory is that the cheaper the price, the more increased sales become has no effect on the relationship between these two variables. There are similar research results; price reasonableness does not have a positive and significant on repurchase interest due to an economically regulated price strategy (Buranasompob, n.d., 2021).

In this study, the amount of tuition fees did not affect the decision of parents to register and continue to join Amaniyah Tutoring Institute. The results of the study revealed implicitly that Bimbel Amaniyah consumers are more concerned with quality than the low fees of education. So, the more quality in teaching and learning activities held, the more likely parents are to continue to register at Amaniyah Tutoring Institute.

➤ *The Influence of Service Quality toward Repurchase Intention*

The results of hypothesis testing previously showed that the service quality has a positive and significant effect toward repurchase intention. It fits by the research conducted by Shin et al., (2019) the quality of educational service effects the decision to repurchase intention for diving/scuba diving lessons. The same result happened by Leonnard's research (2018), that the quality of service effects the students decision to repurchase.

The test results interpreted that the parents of Amaniyah Tutoring Institute had felt the good quality of service, thus ensure them make the repurchase intention. The underlying factors are the interaction of parents with tutors during the

parental decision-making period, the process of registering new students, and the process of providing information about student learning progress, both carried out by call center and tutors, has made a deep good impression.

By paying attention to the effects of these dimensions on service quality on the decision to repurchase, managers need to consider the delivery of service quality which includes attitudes, behaviors, and communication skills of call center and tutors at Bimbel Amaniyah as frontliners who interact with parents and students directly.

A further implication of the effects of service quality on repurchase intention is that high service quality will support the desire of parents. So whenever the students completed the learning program taken, they will continue to take another learning program at Bimbel Amaniyah. The parents who have more than a child, it will be possible to enroll the other children in Amaniyah Tutoring Institute. Therefore, the quality of services like this must be maintained in order to continue to have a positive and significant effects on repurchase intention.

➤ *The Influence of Promotion, Tuition Fees, and Service Quality toward Repurchase Intention through Customer Satisfaction*

Based on the results, customer satisfaction does not mediate the relationship between promotion, tuition fees, and service quality toward repurchase intention.

In this study, no mediation effect occurred. The determining factor variable for the non-implementation of customer satisfaction mediation is that service quality does not have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction, especially in the call center. Less responsive to replying to parents' messages. Another factor is that the tuition fees does not have a positive and significant effect toward repurchase intention, and the satisfaction that consumers feel is not able to increase the ratio of repurchase intention.

Although several previous studies have proven that consumer satisfaction can increase the ratio of consumers to support repurchase (Alfonsius et al., 2021; Choi et al., 2019; Phuong & Trang, 2018). However, research conducted on parents of Amaniyah Tutoring Institute students showed the opposite result. Similar research results are also proven to universities by Yani & Kuswardani (2021), that consumer satisfaction cannot be a mediator for the decision to repurchase.

Consumer satisfaction has a very intense dynamic with the repurchase intention. In this study, the increased satisfaction that parents felt could not bridge the incessant promotion, tuition fees and quality of services carried out by Amaniyah Tutoring Institute in influencing the repurchase intention. It can be interpreted that although parents are satisfied with promotions, and tuition fees, it is not able to effect the decision of parents to continue studying at Amaniyah Tutoring Institute.

In addition, there are several factors that can cause the halt in the desire of parents to choose again. When students graduate after taking their course, parents – at the student's own final discretion – decide that students 'take a break' before starting a new course of study. This often happens to students who learn to read and are reluctant to continue other learning programs such as Quantum Math Fun, Brilliant English Course, and Mapel.

Another factor is the economic reason, as researchers encountered when conducting pre-surveys. The parents were satisfied with the promotion and services implemented by Amaniyah Tutoring Institute, but the family's faltering financial situation became a careful consideration.

Another implication in this study is that at certain levels of education, students no longer have the opportunity to continue to join Amaniyah Tutoring Institute because of the unavailability of learning programs that they can take. For example, for students who graduate from junior high school who want to take vocational schools in nursing, midwifery, and aviation. The same thing can happen to high school graduates who want to take courses in Philology, Biology, Physics and Japanese Language. This situation has the general consequence that they are no longer able to continue studying at Amaniyah Tutoring Institute.

VI. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

A. Conclusion

- Promotion has positive and significant effect toward consumer satisfaction.
- Tuition fees have positive and significant effect toward consumer satisfaction.
- Service quality has negative affect customer satisfaction.
- Promotion has positive and significant effect toward repurchase intention.
- The tuition fees have negative and significant effect toward repurchase intention.
- The service quality has positive and significant effects toward repurchase intention.
- Customer satisfaction does not mediate promotions, tuition fees, and service quality over the repurchase intention.

B. Suggestion

Based on the conclusions above, there are several suggestions given in this study:

➤ Practical suggestion for Amaniyah Tutoring Institute

- On the variable of promotion toward consumer satisfaction, Bimbel Amaniyah should pay attention to the use of social media in displaying interesting content for parents. Do good engagement to students and their parent. The dimensions of public relations and publicity must be improved. Publishing each student's achievements and good reviews from parents on social media.
- On the variable tuition fees toward consumer satisfaction, EDC machine may be alternative payment for parents who want to take advantage of education aid funds by the government.

- On the variable of service quality to customer satisfaction, product knowledge socialization is important to do. All tutors should understand the advantages of each learning program.
- On the promotion variable toward repurchase intention, Amaniyah Tutoring Institute can maximize the potential of sales promotion activities by social media. Holding quizzes for prizes in the form of scholarship vouchers can be an alternative to creating engagement on social media. It is important to remember that scholarship vouchers should have a time limit to encourage voting decisions as well as repurchase intention.
- On the variable tuition fees toward the repurchase intention, the quality of education offered by Amaniyah Tutoring Institute is highly valued by parents so as to eliminate the effects of competitive education costs. Therefore, Amaniyah Tutoring Institute must pay attention to the quality of education. Every program should have the Standard Operational Procedures, and make sure it runs well.
- On the variable Service quality toward repurchase intention, Amaniyah Tutoring Institute needs to implement recruitment and training standards for call center and tutor.
- On the variable consumer satisfaction in mediating the repurchase intention, Amaniyah Tutoring Institute should provide classes for vocational students or students who want to take certain courses, according to their needs.

➤ Academic suggestion for following research

Based on the results of the study, *consumer satisfaction variables were proven not to mediate the relationship among promotion, tuition fees, and service quality toward repurchase intention*. Future research can test other variables such as consumer loyalty, *experiential marketing*, or brand image as mediating variables.

Future research can also develop research models with larger populations and samples, not only limited to one institute, but also to the learning programs national implemented.

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